

Alterations in some haemato-bio-chemical parameters of a fresh water, air breathing fish, *Channa punctatus* (Bloch) under the stress of chronic, sub-lethal dose of nickel

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ABSTRACT

Alterations in some haemato-bio-chemical parameters of a freshwater, air birthing fish, *Channa punctatus* under the stress of chronic, sub-lethal dose (10ppm) of nickel for 60 days were studied. The TEC, haemoglobin% and PCV progressively and significantly decreased, whereas the TLC exhibited a steady and significant increase with an increase in the duration of exposure time. The plasma protein, cholesterol, lipid, glucose and iron decreased steadily and significantly with an increase in the duration of exposure time. But the plasma triglyceride significantly increased after 15 days of exposure and thereafter showed a gradual and significant decrease upto 60 days of exposure. The results show that nickel in a chronic, sub-lethal dose of 10ppm is harmful to the fish and the alterations in different blood parameters may be used as a tool to assess the pathological condition of fish.

Keywords : *Nickel, Channa punctatus, TEC, Hb%, PCV, TLC, Protein, Cholesterol, lipid, triglyceride, glucose, iron.*

INTRODUCTION

Now a day's fish haematology is considered as an important tool to study the physiology and pathology of fishes. Heavy metals bring about a number of alterations in different blood parameters of fish. Heavy metals are natural constituents of the earth's crust. Nickel is one of the major elemental constituent of the earth, constituting approximately 2% by mass. However, it is a minor constituent (0.01%) of the earth's crust (Moore and Ramamoorthy, 1984). Industrial processes, such as, welding, smelting and fabrication of molten metal's can introduce metals into the aquatic environment at concentrations often in excess of recommended threshold limit (Lam *et.al.*, 1985). Ali Mohammad (2004) has reported that the industrial effluents dumped in river Kabul had a

number of toxicological effects on Mahasser, *Tor putitora*.

Witeska (2005) has reported that lead, copper, zinc and cadmium cause a number of haematological alterations in common carp. Maheswaran *et.al.*, (2008) have reported alterations in haematological parameters of *Clarias bratrachus* exposed to mercuric chloride. Vutukuru (2005) found that chromium induced alterations in some haematological parameters of *Labeo rohita*. Ololade and Ogini (2009) have reported that, zinc causes haematological changes in African Catfish, *Clarias gariepinus*. Vinodini and Narayanan (2009) have reported the effects of a combined mixture of Cd, Pb, Cr and Ni on some haematological parameters of common carp, *Cyprinus Carpio*.

Nickel is generally less toxic to fish than copper, mercury, lead, zinc, cadmium, silver, chromium and arsenic. Nanda and Behera (1996) have studied the toxic effects of nickel on some haemato-bio-chemical parameters of *Heteropneustes fossilis*. Fish haematology plays an important role to monitor fish health, pollution load, stress and disease. Hence this piece of investigation was taken-up to find out the toxic effects of nickel on some haemato-bio-chemical parameters of *Channa punctatus*.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

Healthy adult *Channa punctatus* of both sexes weighing between 30-35g and having a length of 12-15cm were collected from the local freshwater sources and acclimatized to the laboratory conditions for 15 days. The water of the medium was changed every alternate day and the physico-chemical characteristic of the water used was analyzed according to APHA. The acclimatized experimental fishes, irrespective of sex were subjected to a chronic, sub-lethal dose of 10ppm nickel concentration for 60 days. Three replications of the experiment and controls were maintained. At the end of 15, 30, 45 and 60 days, blood was drawn from the nickel treated fishes as well as the control fishes by cardiac puncture using a hypodermic syringe previously rinsed with heparin. The blood drawn from several fishes was pooled and transferred into small vials, which were previously rinsed with heparin. The whole blood was used for the estimation of various haematological parameters. The blood sample was centrifuged at 10,000rpm for 20 minutes to separate the plasma to be used for the estimation of biochemical parameters. The values thus obtained have been reflected in Table No.1.

The blood from heparinized vial was used for the estimation of TEC, Hb%, and TLC as per the methods suggested by Shah and Altindag (2004), Drabkin (1946) and Shah and Altindag (2004) respectively. The PCV was calculated by microhaematocrit or wintrobe's tube method (Ochei and Kolhatkar, 2005). The biochemical parameters like protein, cholesterol, triglyceride and lipid were estimated using the instrument

(analyzer), Kodak Ektachem DT system (C.C.I.S(R), 1994). This system uses dry chemistry technology and dry chemical layer coated slides. All reactions take place within the slide and the test results are automatically printed by an integral printer. Plasma glucose was estimated using O-Toluidine method of Cooper and Mc Daniel (1970). The serum iron estimation was done using a spectrophotometer using the modified method of I.C.S.H. (1990).

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The TEC, Hb% and PCV exhibited a steady and significant decrease with an increase in the duration of exposure to 10ppm nickel. Das and Kaviraj (1990) while working on cadmium toxicity to *Heteropneustes fossilis*; Ololade and Ogini (2009) working on Zinc toxicity to *Clarias gariepinus*; Adeyemo (2007) working on lead toxicity to *Clarias gariepinus* and Nanda and Behera (1996) working on nickel toxicity to *Heteropneustes fossilis* observed similar decrease in TEC, Hb% and PCV. Apart from metals, pesticides and herbicides, such as endosulfen (Tyagi *et.al.*, 1989), atrazine (Ramesh *et.al.*, 2009) and monocrotophos (Yazi and Auta, 2007) also significantly decreased the TEC, Hb% and PCV in fishes. In contrast to these findings Ishikawa *et.al.*, (2007) and Alwan *et.al.*, (2009) reported increase in TEC, Hb% and PCV of fishes exposed to mercury and aluminium respectively. The reduction in some haematological values indicated anaemia and it may be due to erythropoiesis, haemosynthesis and osmoregulatory dysfunction or due to an increase in the rate of erythrocyte destruction in the haemopoietic organs (Jenkins *et.al.* 2003; Seth and Saxena, 2003). Joshi *et.al.*, (2002) were of the opinion that inhibition of erythropoiesis and increase in the rate of erythrocyte destruction in haemopoietic organs is the cause of decrease in TEC and related parameters.

The TLC showed a gradual but significant increase on exposure to chronic, sub-lethal dose of nickel for 60 days. Nanda and Behera (1996) also reported an increase in the TLC of *Heteropneustes fossilis* exposed to nickel. Maheswaran *et.al.*, (2008) reported similar

Parameters	Control "0"ppm	15 days	Control "0"ppm	30 days	Control "0"ppm	45 days	Control "0"ppm	60 days
RBC x10 ⁶ /cmm	3.42 ± 0.42	2.96 ± 0.08*	3.28 ± 0.32	2.28 ± 0.02*	3.38 ± 0.26	1.98 ± 0.02*	3.28 ± 0.18	1.54 ± 0.01*
WBC x10 ³ /cmm	10.48 ± 0.38	11.78 ± 0.32*	10.5 ± 0.26	12.82 ± 0.36*	10.36 ± 0.30	14.32 ± 0.28*	10.28 ± 0.32	15.68 ± 0.3*
Haemoglobin %	9.56 ± 0.20	8.42 ± 0.20*	9.46 ± 0.18	7.26 ± 0.16*	9.48 ± 0.16	6.64 ± 0.12*	9.52 ± 0.18	5.48 ± 0.08*
Haematocrit %	38.8 ± 0.68	36.24 ± 0.46*	38.6 ± 0.76	35.18 ± 0.36*	38.5 ± 0.62	34.12 ± 0.18*	38.7 ± 0.70	32.62 ± 0.2*
Total protein mg/dl	8.30 ± 0.28	7.12 ± 0.18*	8.26 ± 0.38	6.48 ± 0.12*	8.16 ± 0.28	5.68 ± 0.10*	8.2 ± 0.18	4.92 ± 0.0*
Glucose mg/dl	54.52 ± 0.82	53.68 ± 0.68**	54.68 ± 0.96	52.46 ± 0.52*	54.48 ± 0.88	51.12 ± 0.78*	54.58 ± 0.82	49.16 ± 0.7*
Cholesterol mg/dl	54.62 ± 0.92	52.46 ± 0.82*	54.28 ± 0.96	51.62 ± 0.76*	54.46 ± 0.92	50.48 ± 0.72*	54.56 ± 0.86	48.62 ± 0.6*
Lipid mg/dl	68.8 ± 0.46	66.62 ± 0.52*	68.6 ± 0.58	65.78 ± 0.42*	68.5 ± 0.52	64.92 ± 0.44*	68.7 ± 0.50	63.48 ± 0.3*
Triglyceride mg/dl	30.26 ± 0.38	31.48 ± 0.28*	30.2 ± 0.48	30.62 ± 0.26**	30.32 ± 0.42	29.28 ± 0.24***	30.28 ± 0.32	28.68 ± 0.2*
Iron mg/dl	54.68 ± 0.48	51.48 ± 0.62*	54.38 ± 0.46	50.12 ± 0.58*	54.48 ± 0.40	48.62 ± 0.38*	54.52 ± 0.38	46.32 ± 0.3*

Table 1. Changes in some haematological parameters of *Channa punctatus* after prolonged exposure to sub-lethal concentration (10ppm) of Nickel. n=20. N.S. = Not significant, * = P < 0.001, ** = P < 0.01, * = P < 0.05**

increase in TLC of *Clarias batrachus* exposed to mercuric chloride. Adeyemo (2007) also noted similar increase in TLC of *Clarias gariepinus* treated with lead. Vosyliene and Jankaite (2006) reported an increase in the TLC of rainbow trout exposed to heavy metal model mixture (Cu, Zn, Ni, Cr, Pb etc.). Certain organophosphates also lead to an increase in the TLC in fishes (Yaji and Auta, 2007; Ramesh and Saravanan, 2008 and Ramesh *et.al.* 2009).

In contrast to the above findings Witeska (2005) noted a decrease in the TLC of common carp exposed to various heavy metals. Ololade and Ogini (2009) observed a decrease in the TLC of *Clarias gariepinus* exposed to zinc. Ishikawa *et.al.* (2007) have reported decrease in TLC of *Oreochromis niloticus* on exposure to mercury. The increase in TLC on exposure to various heavy metals may be caused by liver dysfunction and depression. It may also be due to tissue damage and subsequent removal of debris by W.B.C. cells (Goel and Gupta, 1985). The increase in TLC under different metallic stress, however, has been considered as an adaptation to meet the stressful condition.

The serum protein content showed a gradual and significant decrease with an increase in the exposure period to 10ppm nickel. Maheswaran

et.al. (2008) working on the toxicity of mercury on *Clarias batrachus*; Ololade and Ogini (2009) working on zinc toxicity to *Clarias gariepinus* and Adeyemo (2007) while working on the toxicity of lead to *Clarias gariepinus* observed similar decrease in protein. Nanda and Behera (1996) also obtained similar decrease in protein, when they exposed *Heteropneustes fossilis* to nickel. This decrease in serum protein may be due to malfunctioning of the liver and reduced protein synthesis or protein breakdown (Sen *et.al.*, 1992).

The serum cholesterol and triglyceride exhibited a progressive and significant decrease with an increase in the exposure period to 10ppm nickel. Sen *et.al.* (1992) and Martinez *et.al.* (2004) have reported decrease in the cholesterol and triglyceride levels in fishes treated with zinc and lead respectively. Vutukuru (2005) has reported an appreciable decline in the serum lipid of the fish under chromium stress. Shova *et.al.* (2007) have also reported similar decrease in lipid content in *Catla catla* exposed to cadmium. But Nanda and Behera (1996) observed that the cholesterol, lipid and triglyceride increased in the nickel treated *Heteropneustes fossilis*. Zaki *et.a.* (2008) while working on the effect of lead on *Oreochromis niloticus* observed that, the cholesterol, lipid and triglyceride increased. The

decrease may be due to malfunctioning of the liver, which esterifies it and excretes a part of it after its conversion into cholic acid with bile. The decrease in lipid content may also be due to inhibition of lipid synthesis by various toxicants, as well as increased utilization of stored lipids as a source of energy to conduct normal metabolic functions.

There was a significant decrease in the serum glucose level in *Channa punctatus* under chronic, sub-lethal dose of 10ppm nickel. Kumar and Pant (1981) observed depletion in the serum glucose level in *Puntias conchinus* exposed to copper and zinc. Ramesh *et.al*, (2009) obtained similar results in *Cyprinus carpio* exposed to atrazine, an herbicide. In contrast to the above findings Vinodini and Narayanan (2009) observed an elevation of the serum glucose level in *Cyprinus carpio* on exposure to some toxic heavy metals. Zaki *et.al*, (2008) have reported an increase in serum glucose in *Oreochromis niloticus* exposed to lead. This decrease in glucose contents reflects the changes in carbohydrate metabolism under hypoxia and stress conditions.

The serum iron content showed a progressive and significant decrease with an increase in the exposure period to a sub-lethal dose of 10ppm nickel. Gupta (1979) observed that the serum iron level decreased in mercury and lead treated *Ophiocephalus punctatus* and *Heteropneustes fossilis* respectively. In contrast to the above findings, Vinodini and Narayanan (2009) observed an increase in the serum iron content in *Cyprinus carpio* treated with toxic heavy metals. The decrease in serum iron as noted during the present investigation may be due to destruction of erythrocytes by haemolysis under nickel stress.

Finally the present study suggests that the alterations in the blood indices may be attributed to a defence reaction against toxicity of nickel and may be due to the disturbances that occurred in both metabolic and haemopoitic activities of fish exposed to nickel.

REFERENCES

1. Adeyemo, O. K. (2007): Haematological profile of *Clarias gariepinus* (Burchell) exposed to lead; *Turkish J. Fish. Aquat. Sci.*; **7**: 163- 169.
2. Ali Mohammad Yousafzai (2004): Toxicological effects of industrial effluents dumped in river "Kabul" on Mahaseer, *Tor putitora* at Amangarh industrial area, Peshawar, Pakistan, unpublished Ph. D. thesis, University of Punjab, Lahore.
3. Alwan, S.F.; Hadi, A.A. and Shokr, A. E. (2009): Alterations in haematological parameters of freshwater fish, *Tilapia zilli*, exposed to aluminium; *J. Sci. Appl.*; **3(1)**: 12 – 19.
4. APHA (2005): Standard methods for the examination of water and waste water; 21st edition, *American Public Health Association, New York, U.S.A.*
5. CCIS(R).1994: Computerized Clinical Information System, Denver, CO, Micromedex Inc.
6. Cooper, G.R. and Mc Daniel (1970): "Standard methods of Clinical Chemistry" Pp 159.
7. Das, B.K and Kaviraj A. (1990): Accumulation of cadmium in *Heteropneustes fossilis* and changes in haematological parameter, *J.Natcon.*: **2(1)** :25-30
8. Drabkin, D.L, 1946: Spectro-photometric studies, XIV- the crystallographic and optical properties of the Haemoglobin of man in comparison with those of other species; *J. Biol. Chem.*; **164**: 703-723
9. Goel, K.A. and Gupta, K. (1985): Zinc toxicity to a freshwater teleost *Clarias batrachus*; *Ind. J Fish.*; **32(2)** : 256 – 259.
10. Gupta, P.K.(1979): Toxic effects of two heavy metals mercury and lead on the digestive system of *Ophiocephalus punctatus* and *Heteropneustes fossilis*; Ph.D. thesis, Meerut University, Meerut.
11. I.C.S.H. (1980): Recommendation for reference method for determination by centrifugation of packed cell volume of blood, *Jour Clinical Pathol.*; **33** : 1

12. Ishikawa, N.M. Ranjani-Paiva, M.J.T.; Lombardi, J.V. and Ferrira, C.M. (2007): Haematological parameters in Nile tilapia, *Oreochromis niloticus* exposed to sub-lethal concentration of mercury; *Braz. Arch. Biol. Technol.*; **50(4)**: 619 – 626.
13. Jenkins, F.; Smith, J. *et al.*, (2003): Effect of sub-lethal concentrations of endosulfan on haematological and serum biochemical parameters in the Carp, *Cyprinus carpio*; *Bull. Environ. Contam. Toxicol.*; **70** : 993 – 997.
14. Joshi,P.K.; Bose, M. and Harish,D. (2002): Changes in certain haematological parameters in a siluroid Catfish; *Clarias batrachus* ; exposed to cadmium chloride ; *Pollut . Res.*; **21(2)**:129–131.
15. Kumar, S. and Pant, S.C. (1981): Histopathologic effect of acutely toxic levels of Copper and Zinc on gill, liver and kidney of *Puntias conchinus*; *Ind. J. Exp. Biol.*; **19**: 191 – 194.
16. Lam, H.; Conner, M.; Rogers, A.; Fitzgerald, S. and Admur, M. (1985): Functional changes in the lungs of *Guneapig* exposed to zinc oxide; *Toxicol. Appl. Pharmacol.* : **78**: 29.
17. Maheswaran, R. Devapaul., A.; Muralidharan, S. Velmurugan, B. and Ignacimuthu, S. (2008): Haematological studies of freshwater fish, *Clarias batrachus (L.)* exposed to mercuric chloride. *Intl. J. Integ. Biol.*; **2(1)**: 49 – 54.
18. Martinez, C.B.R.; Nagae, M.Y.; Zaia, C.T.B.V. and Zaia, D.A.M. (2004): Acute morphological and physiological effects of lead in the Neotropical fish, *Prochilodus lineatus.*; *Braz. J.Biol.*; **64(4)**: 797 – 807.
19. Moore, J.W. and Ramamoorthy, S. (1984): Heavy metals in natural waters; applied monitoring and impact assessment; *Springer*, New-York; Pp. 268.
20. Nanda, P. and Behera, M.K. (1996): Nickel induced changes in some haemato-biochemical parameter of a Catfish, *Heteropneustes fossilis* (Bloch); *Enviorn and Ecol.*; **14(1)**: 82 – 85.
21. Ochei, J. and Kolhatkar, A.(2005): “Medical Laboratory Science-Theory and Practical” –Tata Mcgraw Hill publishing Company , New Delhi; Pp 281-283.
22. Ololade, I.A., and Oginni, O. (2009): Behavioural and haematological effects of Zinc on African Cat fish, *Clarias gariepinus*, *Intl. J. Fish. Aquat.*; **1(2)**: 22 – 27.
23. Ramesh, M. and Saravanan, M. (2008): Haematological and biochemical responses in a freshwater fish, *Cyprinus carpio* exposed to Chlorpyrifos; *Intl. J.Integra. Biol.*; **3(1)**: 80 – 83.
24. Ramesh, M.; Srinivasan, R. and Saravanan, M. (2009): Effect of atrazine (Herbicide) on blood parameters of common carp, *Cyprinus carpio* (Actinopterygii: cypriniformes); *African J. Environ. Sci. Technol.*; **3(12)**: 453 – 458.
25. Sen, G.; Behera, M.K. and Patel, P.N. (1992): Effect of zinc on haemato-biochemical parameters of *Channa punctatus*; *J. Ecotoxicol. Environ. Monit.*; **2**:89–92.
26. Seth, N. and Saxena, K.K. (2003): Haematological responses in a freshwater fish, *Channa punctatus* due to fenvalerate; *Bull. Environ. Contam. Toxicol.*; **71**: 1192 – 1199.
27. Shah, S.L. and Altindag, A. (2004): Haematological parameters of tench (*Tinca tinca*) after acute and chronic exposure to lethal and sub-lethal mercury treatments. *Bull. Environ. Contam. Toxicol.*; **73**: 911 – 918.
28. Sobha, K.; Poornima, A.; Harini, P. and Veeraiah, K. (2007): A study on biochemical changes in the freshwater fish, *Catla catla* exposed to the heavy metal toxicant cadmium chloride; *Kathmandu Univ. J.Sci. Engg. Technol.*; **1(4)**: 1 – 11.
29. Tyagi, M. Agrawal, V.P. and Nandini, M. (1989): Haematological abnormalities induced in *Ophiocephalus punctatus* by endosulfan, *Recent trend in Toxicol.*; Pp. 81 – 84.
30. Vinodhini, R. and Narayanan, M. (2008): Bioaccumulation of heavy metals in Organs of freshwater fish, *Cyprinus carpio*; *Int. J. Environ. Sci.Tech*; **5(2)**: 179 – 182.
31. Vosyliene, M.Z. and Jankaite, A. (2006): Effect of heavy metal model mixture on rainbow trout biological parameters; *Ekologija*; **4** : 12 – 17.

32. Vutukuru, S.S. (2005): Acute effects of hexavalent chromium on survival, Oxygen consumption, haematological parameters and some biochemical profiles of the Indian major carp, *Labeo rohita*; *Int.J. Environ. Res Public Health*; **2(3)**:456 – 462.
33. Witeska, M. (2005): Stress in fish – haematological and immunological effects of heavy metals; *Elect. J. Ichthyol.*; **1**:35–41.
34. Yaji, A.J. and Auta, J. (2007): Sub-lethal effects of monocrotophos on some haematological indices of African Catfish, *Clarias gariepinus* (*Teungels*) ; *J. Fish . Intl.*; **2(1)**:115–117
35. Zaki, S.M.; Sharaf, N.E. and Osfer, M.H. (2007): Effect of vanadium toxicity on biochemical, haematological and clinic pathological changes in *Clarias lazera* present in the river Nile; *Amer–Eurasian J.Agric. Environ. Sci.*; **2(6)**:741–745.

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